

Manipulation of Magnetic Nanoparticles by Optically Induced Dielectrophoresis

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Abstract—This paper presents a method for the manipulation of magnetic nanoparticles by optically induced dielectrophoresis (ODEP) device that can realize the transportation and convergence of nanoparticles. ODEP can be realized with a sandwich structure of three layers including the photoconductive layer, the liquid layer with the sample and the indium tin oxide electrode (ITO) layer. In this work, magnetic nanoparticles with the diameter of 10-100nm were successfully manipulated by positive dielectrophoresis force. The solution with magnetic nanoparticles on a mica substrate placed in the sandwich structure was dried in the air and imaged by atomic force microscope (AFM). The AFM images showed that the magnetic nanoparticles were converged in the illumination area. This method can be used to manipulate magnetic nanoparticles.

Keyword—ODEP; magnetic nanoparticles; manipulation; atomic force microscope (AFM)

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the magnetic nanoparticles [1-3] have been widely used in many areas due to their advantages of good biocompatibility, hypotoxicity, easy functionalization, and super paramagnetism. The targeted gene therapy, biosensors [4], magnetic fever treatment [5-6] and drug delivery [7] are some of application examples. The automatic assembly of the magnetic nanoparticles is also important. A number of methods for the manipulation of magnetic nanoparticles have been studied. Chitu et al composed a 3-D structure of Co nanoparticles by drying a droplet of colloidal solution of nanoparticles to the substrate in a magnetic field [8]. Usov et al observed the motion of magnetic nanoparticles in external magnetic field, and they found that the unit magnetization vector and director were approximately along the external magnetic field in the high-frequency mode and nearly parallel and rotated in unison around the external magnetic field in the low-frequency mode [9]. Wilhelm et al demonstrated that different magnetic field solicitations could realize the manipulation of magnetic nanoparticles at the intracellular level which was used to heat the cell from its inside or probe the cell architecture [10]. Anker et al used magnetic tweezers to assemble the suspensions of fluorescent chemical sensors containing magnetic pH sensitive particles into groups or “swarms” of sensors, which formed an intermediate architecture between uncontrolled photonic explorers for

bioanalysis is with biologically localized embedding (PEBBLEs) and rigid fiber optic sensors [11]. Mironov et al used magnetic force microscope (MFM) probe to control the chirality of a magnetic vortex in elliptical $400 \times 600 \times 27$ nm Co particles [12]. In recent years, an optically induced dielectrophoresis (ODEP) device was used to manipulate micro/nanoparticles [13-14], cells [15-21], DNA [23] and fabricate the micrometer- and nanometer scale polymer structures [22]. It can be realized with a sandwich structure of three layers including the photoconductive layer, the liquid layer with the sample and the indium tin oxide electrode (ITO) layer. When a beam of light is projected onto the photoconductive layer, a virtual electrode is formed and it can move and converge the nanoparticles on the photoconductive surface.

In this work, magnetic nanoparticles with the diameter of 10-100nm were successfully manipulated by positive dielectrophoresis force. The solution with magnetic nanoparticles on a mica substrate placed in the sandwich structure was dried in the air and imaged by atomic force microscope (AFM). The AFM images showed that the magnetic nanoparticles were converged in the illumination area. The details are described in the following sections.

II. THE SCHEMATIC STRUCTURE OF THE ODEP CHIP AND EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

A. The Schematic Structure of the ODEP Chip

Fig.1 is the schematic structure of an ODEP chip. It consists of three layers, the top side is ITO glass, the interlayer is the liquid solution with the magnetic nanoparticles, and the bottom surface is the ITO glass with a photoconductive layer which is hydrogenated amorphous silicon (a:Si-H) with the thickness of 1 μ m. A freshly cleaved mica substrate is pasted to the photoconductive layer with a 50- μ m double-sided tape. An AC voltage is connected across the top and bottom ITO electrodes with two wires using the conducting resin. The a:Si-H layer is non-conductive and its dark conductivity is 10^{-12} – $10^{-10}(\Omega\text{cm})^{-1}$ [24]. The electric field in the solution layer is very weak without illumination. When a beam of light from a projector is projected onto the photoconductive layer, the conductivity of a:Si-H layer at the light area will increase several orders of magnitude and become conductive. A virtual electrode is created in the illuminated area and a non-uniform electric field is generated.

The magnetic particles can be absorbed under the positive ODEP force.

Fig. 1 Schematic structure of the ODEP chip.

B. Experimental Setup

(a)

(b)

Fig. 2 (a) ITO chip. (b) A photoconductive chip.

Fig. 2(a) and Fig. 2(b) are 30mm×30mm ITO glass and the ITO glass with a photoconductive layer chip. The thickness of ITO layer was 200nm and the glass thickness was 2mm. The photoconductive layer a-Si:H was deposited on the ITO glass by plasma-enhanced chemical vapor deposition (PECVD) method with the thickness of 1μm, and the ITO glass edge was exposed in the air for contacting with an electrical source, as shown in Fig. 2(b).

Fig. 3 shows the experiment setup. The microscope

(Navitar ZOOM 600, Navitar) was used to observe and determine the illuminated position which is convenient to find suitable area when the sample was scanned using AFM, and the current time screenage of the solution with magnetic nanoparticles was recorded in computer 1. A beam of light was projected to a 10× objective by a projector (EB-X8, Epson) and reflected to ODEP chip by a mirror forming a virtual electrode. The shape of virtual electrode was decided by the standard presentation software (Microsoft Power Point) in computer 2 connected with the projector. A function generator (EM1644, Yi Fei) was used to provide the AC signal to the ODEP chip.

Fig. 3 The experiment set up for manipulating magnetic nanoparticles.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The mica substrate was stripped with white transparent tapes for obtaining a complete layer, then cleaned with ultrasonic washer for 2 minutes and dried in the air, and it was labeled by a red making pen which was easy to find the convergent position of magnetic nanoparticles when it was observed under AFM. The mica substrate was placed in the sandwich structure after 0.25μl solution with magnetic nanoparticles was dripped onto it and immobilized on the photoconductive layer with a 50-μm double-sided tape. 5μg/mL Fe₃O₄ magnetic nanoparticles with the diameter of 10-100 nm, synthesized by the co-precipitation method, were functioned by acetate and dispersed by ultrasounds. A 0.25μl pipette from Brand was used to obtain or drip the solution of magnetic nanoparticles. A beam of light with a linetype drawn with Microsoft Power Point was projected onto the ODEP chip. The Agilent 5500 scanning probe microscope (SPM) from the Agilent Technologies was used to obtain the AFM images of the magnetic nanoparticles. The ContA1 AFM probes from BudgeSensors with the tip radius less than 10nm and force constant 0.2N/m were used in the experiment.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The AFM images of magnetic nanoparticles are shown in Fig. 4. The scanned area was 80μm×80μm, the scanned frequency was 0.8Hz, the image size was 512×512, the IGain and PGain are 2, and the tapping mode was used for AFM imaging. An AC signal with the frequency 50kHz and 2v peak-to-peak was applied on the plane electrodes. When the

AC signal and illumination were not applied to the ODEP chip, the solution of magnetic nanoparticles on the mica substrate was naturally dried in the air, and the distribution of magnetic nanoparticles on the mica substrate is shown in Fig. 4 (a). Due to the thermal motion and Brownian movement of the magnetic nanoparticles in the solution, the random distribution of magnetic nanoparticles was observed by AFM after the sample was air-dried. Fig. 4(b) shows the image of magnetic nanoparticles under the ODEP field. The light from projector was delivered to the sample in a straight line, and the photoconductive layer generated electron-hole pairs on the illumination area and the conductivity of a:Si-H was increased to $\sim 10^{-5}$ – $10^{-4}(\Omega\text{cm})^{-1}$ from 10^{-12} – $10^{-10}(\Omega\text{cm})^{-1}$. A nonuniform electric field was created in the liquid layer, and the magnetic nanoparticles in the solution were induced and moved toward the light under the positive ODEP force, and converged into a straight line.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4 AFM images of magnetic nanoparticles. (a) AFM image of magnetic nanoparticles without the ODEP field; (b) AFM image of magnetic nanoparticles under the ODEP field

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, magnetic nanoparticles with the diameter of 10-100nm were successfully manipulated by positive dielectrophoresis force. The solution of magnetic

nanoparticles on a mica substrate placed in the sandwich structure was dried in the air and imaged by AFM, and the AFM images showed that the magnetic nanoparticles were converged in the illumination area. The result has shown that this method can be used to manipulate magnetic nanoparticles. This method can be used to manipulate magnetic nanoparticles.

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